

PROCESSES OF FORMATION OF ECOLOGICAL CULTURE IN PRE-SCHOOL CHILDRENS

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ABSTRACT: *The article is devoted to describing the foundations of environmental culture in children of senior preschool age. The ecological culture of preschoolers is considered as an integrative personal education, including interconnected components such as: cognitive and emotional-value, etc. It was shown that the education of environmental culture is defined as purposeful pedagogical work to develop in children environmental knowledge and ideas, a respectful attitude towards natural objects and appropriate behavior skills in nature. The proposed program for developing an environmental culture among older preschoolers includes a set of classes on ecology with elements of experimentation and methodological support of educational work in a preschool institution on environmental education of children.*

Keywords: *ecological culture, children of senior preschool age, educational program, ecology classes, methodological support*

INTRODUCTION

The basis of ecological culture is environmental morality - awareness of the need to coordinate one’s actions (or the actions of a group of people) with the interests of nature, the perception of natural resources as common human wealth. As for environmental management, only such actions in relation to nature that do not destroy it can be recognized as moral. In order for schoolchildren to learn to love nature, admire its beauty, learn to protect and fight for its conservation, active environmental activities are carried out. Currently, relatively new types of educational activities of a complex nature for younger schoolchildren are spreading: educational and research, project-based. Today, additional conditions have been introduced for the implementation of educational research and projects, namely the introduction of additional hours of extracurricular work. There is no need to expect “adult forms” of manifestations of environmental culture from younger schoolchildren. But if, as a result of pedagogical work, the child knows the rules of environmental ethics, evaluates the emotional impressions of perceiving pictures of nature, shows interest in knowledge, reads stories about nature, sings songs, then we can say that the problem has been solved. And the teacher must create conditions for children to grow up ideologically mature, morally stable and spiritually rich.

The concept of environmental education states that the formation of the foundations of environmental culture as a personality trait presupposes:

- formation of knowledge about the unity of nature, its significance for human life, about interaction in the human-nature-society system;
- formation of intellectual and practical skills for studying, assessing, and improving the environment;
- encouragement of value orientations of the environment;
- formation of motives, needs, skills of appropriate behavior and activities, skills of scientific and moral judgments on environmental issues;
- participation in active practical activities for environmental protection [1].

It should be noted that the ecological culture of children is formed only under favorable social conditions in the family, kindergarten, school, and the immediate natural and socio-cultural environment. Both soil and moisture for the plant, and a favorable environment for the development of the child are of great importance: in a bad environment the child is spoiled and languishes. But each seed needs its own soil and this or that moisture, and when caring for a plant, you need to take into account what kind of seed it is and what the laws of its growth are. And the relationship of a plant, like any living creature, to the environment is active. He takes and assimilates one thing from the environment, but does not accept another. This itself, in turn, influences and creates the environment. In an incomparably more active form, the child does the same. Educators consider environmental culture as a culture of unity between man and nature, a harmonious fusion of social needs and the needs of people with the normal existence and development of the environment. Therefore, he needs to master scientific knowledge, learn moral value orientations in relation to nature, and also develop practical skills and abilities to preserve favorable environmental conditions [2].

A major cognitive and educational role in the formation of a caring attitude of primary schoolchildren towards the natural environment is played by the disclosure of the term “nature conservation” as an activity aimed at preserving and increasing natural resources. In the lessons “The World Around us”, when forming goals, the content of the sections pays great attention to issues of environmental protection. The essence of the concept of “nature conservation,” unfortunately, is not specified in relation to the age-related capabilities of younger schoolchildren, both in terms of understanding and organizing children’s participation in practical classes, although it is outlined in the content of the topics [3-6].

The content of moral norms and rules of human behavior in the natural environment is revealed to children gradually, as we study the issues of protecting specific natural objects. Using illustrative examples, children learn to understand what can and cannot be done in nature so as not to cause undesirable consequences. A necessary element in the formation of a caring attitude towards nature is a holistic aspect, which reveals the diverse role of nature in human life and is the most

important motive for preserving nature. Thus, when teaching reading, the aesthetic side of protecting the nature of their native land is emphasized, and students' ability to aesthetically perceive the beauty of nature is developed. The same problem is solved when teaching fine arts. At the same time, in the lessons of labor education and natural science, some issues of environmental protection are considered only from a “useful” point of view. In this regard, the need to use interdisciplinary connections in environmental education and upbringing of junior schoolchildren is obvious in order to show children the beauty of nature, its educational, entertaining and practical activities, to awaken their desire to protect it as a source of beauty, joy, inspiration, as a condition for the existence of humanity .

In the “World around us” lessons, much attention is paid to developing children's knowledge about the rules of individual behavior in nature. It is explained to students that compliance with the rules of behavior when communicating with nature is one of the most important measures for protecting nature. An important example of developing children's knowledge about the rules of behavior in nature are exercises on applying these rules in practice. When studying nature, excursions are conducted to familiarize and study the surface and vegetation of the surrounding area in order to determine their characteristics. But all the work will only influence the feelings and development of students if they have their own experience of communicating with nature. Therefore, excursions, walks and hikes should occupy a large place in the work system to foster a love of nature. They can be related to the study of program material, have a local history nature, or they can simply be devoted to getting to know nature. But it should be borne in mind that during excursions into nature we must also solve the problems of aesthetic education.

Typically, nature conservation is limited to questions about green areas. It also needs to be considered much more broadly. During excursions and walks, children may encounter, for example, contaminated sources. Cleaning up the source of waste is everyone's business. If the excursion is carried out in an area where the surface is characterized by ravines and gullies, then here too the children can put their strength into fighting the ravines. It is extremely important to teach children to look for such useful things on their own. Before the field trip, the teacher helps the children organize work groups, each of which receives his assignment. It is important that in all groups there are children who are already well acquainted with the characteristics of their region, and children who are not interesting to them. The organization of tasks may vary. In one case, group members perform different tasks: some collect plants for a collection, others collect rocks [7,8].

Environmental activities at school occupy a special place and include: environmental raids aimed at identifying violations; collection and dissemination of environmental information about nearby ecosystems; involving children and the

public in environmental activities and environmental education of the population; protection of the natural environment (feeding birds, animals, rescuing animals, fighting garbage, making feeders); improvement of the natural environment (planting plants, landscaping streets, strengthening the slopes of ravines, clearing forests of dry wood); preventing and combating negative actions in nature (green patrols); propaganda and explanation of environmental ideas (conversations with friends, parents, making posters); preservation and use of aesthetic values of nature (collecting natural materials, making handicrafts); studying the natural environment (participation in school environmental monitoring, research).

Unfortunately, much in this matter depends on each person’s awareness of the need to respect the environment and responsibility for its preservation. Everyone needs to understand the value of nature, know the rational use of nature, understand the relationship between the environment and human health, know the environmental problems of your area, follow the rules of behavior in nature, participate in socially useful work to study and preserve nature in your area [9,10] . The results of the diagnostic cross-section showed that schoolchildren in the experimental group had developed environmental knowledge about theoretical methods of study (76%) and practical ones (52%). However, not all schoolchildren connect theoretical knowledge with practice (24%). The need to use environmental knowledge and skills in practice to solve environmental problems is more strongly expressed (55%). Teenagers are able to select the necessary methods for studying plant communities (52%) and determine the necessary tools for research (56%). The results of the test tasks showed a positive trend in the quality of students’ knowledge (30% before the experiment; 66% after the experiment). Teenagers showed good awareness of environmental problems at the local and regional level. The most important environmental problems identified are: air pollution (22%), water pollution (24%), environmental pollution (19%), chemical waste emissions (16%), radiation (8%), deforestation (6%), garbage on the street (6%), car exhaust gases (4%). Schoolchildren are also thinking about ways to solve environmental problems. Interest in learning has increased. Keeping environmental diaries contributed to the analysis of observations of environmental phenomena. Positive changes were observed in the level of communication culture in the natural environment. The environmental activities of teenagers have become creative. Teenagers have developed an interest in disseminating environmental knowledge in the social environment. Many of them showed initiative in organizing environmental education events, as well as high activity in environmental activities (94%). By participating in professional tests for guides, schoolchildren became involved in the development of an “ecological trail” in the city park and took part in the preparation of environmental and local history excursions. Using this technique, it is possible to

identify the motives for environmental activities. The results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Level of development of motives for environmental activities	Score range	Number of students, %			
		Before the experiment	After the experiment	Before the experiment	After the experiment
Level of formation		Experimental group	Experimental group	Control group	Control group
High level	81-100	32	59	38	33
Average level	61-80	24	20	22	32
Low level	41-60	41	25	36	37

As we can see, there is a positive trend in the level of development of motives for environmental activities among adolescents in the experimental group. There have been positive changes in the development of aesthetic perception of nature. In their creative reports, children used a variety of artistic means: poems, fairy tales, drawings, photographs of landscapes, etc. The results of the study revealed an average level of formation of the emotional component. Thus, the use of criteria for measuring the level of environmental culture in adolescents made it possible to identify the average level of development of this integral quality among students in the experimental group.

CONCLUSION

Thus, we came to the conclusion that the theoretical foundations of environmental education are based on solving problems in their unity: training and education, development. The criterion for developing a responsible attitude towards the environment is moral concern for future generations. Correctly using various teaching methods, a teacher can form an environmentally literate and educated person. Many modern teachers deal with the problems of environmental education and education of junior schoolchildren. Systematic work on environmental protection at school contributes to expanding knowledge about nature, diversifying personality, deep knowledge of one's region and nurturing love for one's native nature.

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